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Liability regulations and respective challenges in the European Union regarding the use of Artificial Intelligence tools

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) advancements present both innovative opportunities and potential risks, particularly concerning opaque decision-making. The European Union (EU) aims to address these challenges through proposed legal frameworks such as the AI Liability Directive and revisions to the Product Liability Directive, alongside the AI Act. These regulations respond to the complexities of assigning liability in AI-related harm cases, where traditional legal frameworks are difficult to apply due to AI's inherent characteristics, such as black-box and lack of causality. Ensuring conformity with fundamental rights and public interest, these frameworks seek to balance innovation with accountability. However, challenges persist in

determining liability when AI-driven systems cause harm, urging for the need to develop transparent AI models that document, explain, and validate decision-making processes. Robust oversight and ongoing education are essential for an ethical use of AI tools that ensure human agency and oversight. While these regulatory efforts signify progress, further steps are needed to establish a trustworthy AI ecosystem within the EU.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is developing rapidly and especially data-driven learning approaches have been innovative in the progress of various technologies in several application fields. However, they also bring several potential risks, such as opaque decision-making (White Paper on AI, 2020). Even though there are safety regulations to reduce these risks, harm can occur (Fernández Llorca et al. 2023), and therefore, this transformation raises questions regarding liability laws in the European Union, leading to the need to explain the assignment of liability.

In general, there are three legal frameworks by which victims can be rewarded for product-induced harm (European Commission, 2019) and that are in general applicable also for AI-induced harm:

- **Fault-based liability:** in principle, the injured parties or claimants must prove that the defendant or wrongdoer caused the harm intentionally or negligently. This requires pointing out the applicable standard the accused should have fulfilled and proving that it was not satisfied.
- **Strict liability:** if a person can use a dangerous object or carry out a dangerous activity for their own objectives, then that person also bears the loss if the risk occurs (Karner, Koch, & Geistfeld, 2021). In this case, the victim does not have to prove the wrongdoing, but only that the risk emerging from the domain of the responsible party occurred.
- **Product liability:** where the injured party can formally request against the producer for a defect present at the time the product was put on the market. Victims must prove that the product was defective (regardless of fault) and the cause and effect linking the defect and the injury. (Vladeck, 2014).

AI systems are risky, namely because they are often opaque (High-level Advisory Body on AI, convened by the United Nations Secretary-General, 2023), unpredictable and lack causality, characteristics that may induce great difficulties when it comes to proving defect or fault and causal link with the harm in the different liability regimes (Fernández Llorca et al. 2023). Liability regimes should be adapted to mitigate the burden of proof on the injured parties when AI technologies are involved. It is still an open question for future investigation, on how to most usefully adjust the responsibility framework to converge the new challenges related to AI systems. Future work could include the development of an official model or procedure to guide possible lines of reasoning in liability cases involving AI systems (Fernández Llorca et al. 2023).

In this regard, the European Commission proposed the first-ever legal framework on AI, trying to address its risks (European Commission, 2021), with two regulations outlining the European approach to AI liability on 28 September 2022: a new AI Liability Directive (AILD) and a revision of the Product Liability Directive (PLD). Simultaneously with the recent AI Act, these new proposals are an advance in the direction of the EU's efforts to make a unified approach to regulating the newest and risks of AI technologies in the EU (Mindy Nunez Duffourc & Sara Gerke, 2023).

This new AI framework establishes some limits to the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (European Commission, 2012) on the freedom to conduct business (Article 16) and the freedom of art and science (Article 13) to guarantee conformity with fundamental reasons of public interest and the protection of other fundamental rights ('responsible innovation') when high-risk AI technology is developed and used. Those restraints are adequate and limited to the minimum necessary to prevent and reduce serious safety risks and likely violations of fundamental rights (European Commission, 2021).

The PLD and AILD are proposed Directives, which still need to be transposed into national laws (TFEU, Art.288), while the AI Act is a proposed regulation which will be directly applicable in all EU Member States. Once transposed into national laws, the two proposed Directives will operate in conjunction with EU Member States existing national (strict and fault-based) laws to govern liability for AI-caused injuries.

The AI and liability regulatory reform above-mentioned aim to respond to the difficulties of the injured person in satisfying the burden of proof on the defectiveness of the product or establishing the causal link between the defect and injuries suffered (Henrique Sousa Antunes, 2023).

AI blurs the lines between traditional product liability (for physical devices) and liability associated with services (software or data-driven services), making it hard to assign liability when an AI-driven device makes an error or causes harm, including identifying whether the responsibility lies with the manufacturer, the developer, the user of the device, or the AI algorithm itself.

The absence of transparency and explainability in AI systems not only hinders post-event accountability but also raises concerns about fairness, bias, and ethical implications. Biases inherent to training data can get amplified within black-box AI systems, potentially resulting in discriminatory decisions that escape scrutiny. Developing interpretable AI models that provide insights into how decisions are reached is crucial. This involves creating algorithms and models designed to elucidate their decision pathways, making the reasoning behind their outputs comprehensible to humans. Techniques like explainable AI (XAI) aim to demystify black-box AI systems by providing understandable justifications or explanations for their outputs. Methods such as feature importance analysis, model visualisation,

or generating decision trees alongside AI predictions can offer insights into the factors influencing specific outcomes.

Moreover, establishing regulations and standards that compel developers and organisations to document, explain, and realistically validate AI models' decision-making processes could mitigate such risks, fostering trust, accountability, and ethical usage of AI, while enabling stakeholders to evaluate and understand AI-driven decisions more effectively.

Also, robust oversight mechanisms need to be established to ensure that AI tools are continuously monitored, validated, and updated to minimise errors and biases (European Commission, 2019). Additionally, ongoing education and training programs for professionals should emphasise the importance of critical thinking, ethical considerations, and the limitations of AI, enabling them to effectively collaborate with AI systems while retaining ultimate decision-making authority.

The new regulatory proposals are a step forward in these subjects at a European level, but challenges still remain (Claudia Nicastro, 2023) and thus additional efforts are needed towards a more trustworthy AI.

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References

- Amann, J., Blasimme, A., Vayena, E., Frey, D., Madai, V. (2020). *Explainability for artificial intelligence in healthcare: a multidisciplinary perspective*. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7706019/>
- Antunes, H. S. (2023). *Non-contractual liability applicable to artificial intelligence: towards a corrective reading of the European intervention*. In *Católica Global School of Law Working Papers No.2/2023*, page 2. <https://catolicalaw.fd.lisboa.ucp.pt/asset/2601/file>

- Duffour, M.N. & Gerke, S. (2023). *The proposed EU Directives for AI liability leave worrying gaps likely to impact medical AI*. NPJ Digital Medicine, 6 Article number:77 published in partnership with Seoul National University Bundang Hospital. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41746-023-00823-w>
- European Commission (2019). *Expert group on liability and new technologies - new technologies formation, liability for artificial intelligence and other emerging digital technologies*. Publications Office of the European Union. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/meetdocs/2014_2019/plmrep/COMMITTEES/JURI/DV/2020/01-09/AI-report_EN.pdf
- European Commission (2020). *White Paper on Artificial Intelligence, A European approach to excellence and trust*, 65 final European Commission page 2. https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2020-02/commission-white-paper-artificial-intelligence-feb2020_en.pdf
- European Commission (2021). *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council - Laying down harmonized rules on artificial Intelligence (AI Act) and amending certain legislative acts*, page 12. In an official EU website. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:e0649735-a372-11eb-9585-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF
- European Commission (2022). *Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on liability for defective products (PLD)*. COM (2022) 495 final.
- European Commission (2022). *Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on adapting non-contractual civil liability rules to artificial intelligence (AI Liability Directive) (AILD)*. In an official EU website. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022PC0496>
- European Commission (2022). *Questions & Answers: AI Liability Directive, in an official EU website*. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_22_5793
- European Commission (2023). *New Product Liability Directive*. In briefing on EU Legislation in progress. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/739341/EPRS_BRI\(2023\)739341_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/739341/EPRS_BRI(2023)739341_EN.pdf)
- European Commission (2019). *Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence*. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>
- European Parliament (2023). *AI Act Briefing* [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/698792/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)698792_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/698792/EPRS_BRI(2021)698792_EN.pdf)
- European Parliament (2023b). *Legislative Train Schedule*. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-europe-fit-for-the-digital-age/file-regulation-on-artificial-intelligence>
- European Union (2012). *Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 2012/C 326/02*. <https://www.refworld.org/docid/3ae6b3b70.html>
- Grant, L. & Pop, F. (2023). *An In-Depth Look at the EU's AI Regulation and Liability Directive*, in EIPA - European Institute of Public Administration. <https://www.eipa.eu/blog/an-in-depth-look-at-the-eus-ai-regulation-and-liability/>
- Hacker, P. (2023). *The European AI Liability Directives – Critique of a Half-Hearted approach and lessons for the future*, Working Paper, in European New School of Digital Studies, European University Viadrina Germany. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.13960>
- Harwood, S. (2023). *EU Artificial Intelligence Liability Directive*, published online in Stephenson Harwood. <https://www.shlegal.com/insights/eu-artificial-intelligence-liability-directive>

- Health Action International (2023). *Fact Sheet – The EU Medical Devices Regulation and the AI Act: a short comparison*. https://haiweb.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/MDR-AIAct_OnePager_FINAL.pdf
- Hedderich, D.M., Weisstanner C., Van Cauter, S., Federau, C., Edjlali M., Radbruch, A., Gerke, S., Haller, S. (2023). *Artificial Intelligence tools in clinical neuroradiology: essential medico-legal aspects*. 65, 1091-1099. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00234-023-03152-7>
- High-level Advisory Body on AI, convened by the United Nations Secretary-General (December 2023) *Interim Report: Governing AI for Humanity*. https://www.un.org/sites/un2.un.org/files/ai_advisory_body_interim_report.pdf
- Hoffmann, M. (2023). *The EU AI Act: A Primer*. <https://cset.georgetown.edu/article/the-eu-ai-act-a-primer/>
- Karner, E., Koch, B.A., & Geistfeld, M.A., (2021) Comparative law study on civil liability for artificial intelligence. European Commission, Directorate-General for justice and Consumers. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/8a32ccc3-0f83-11ec-9151-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>
- Llorca, D.F., Charisi, V., Hamon, R., Sánchez, I., Gómez, E. (2023). *Liability Regimes in the age of AI: a Use-Case Driven Analysis of the Burden of Proof*, in Journal of AI Research Vol.76 (2023) pages 613-644. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1613/jair.1.14565>
- Nicastro, C. (2023). *The EU Liability Directive and product liability Directive*. HAI – Health Action International, Background, page 2. https://haiweb.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/AI-Liability_Background.pdf
- TFEU Art. 288, Consolidated version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union 2012, OJ C326/47 (TFEU). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:12012E/TXT:en:PDF>
- Vladeck, D.C., (2014). *Machines without principals: Liability rules and artificial intelligence*. Washington Law Review, 89(1), 117-150. <https://digitalcommons.law.uw.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=4800&context=wlr>